

DEVELOPMENT AND QUALITY EVALUATION OF PROTEIN RICH VERMICELLI BY INCORPORATION OF WHEAT FLOUR, SPROUTED *MOONG* AND QUINOA FLOURTripti Yadav¹, Devvrat Dixena²¹ Research Scholar, Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur Chhattisgarh, India.triptiyadav.bsp@gmail.com² Food Quality Assurance Officer, Food Ins Lmt., Valsad, Gujrat, India.devvratdixena@gmail.com

MS Received: 27.06.2025; MS Revised: 28.07.2025; MS Accepted: 29.07.2025)

MS 3440

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURE)

Abstract

Vermicelli is prepared by use of whole or refined wheat flour. Dough is prepared, extruded, and dried in the sun. It is a snack food item liked by all age of groups and groups with changing lifestyle. Vermicelli is a popular instant food product falls under the category of extruded product that means it made from extrusion process includes following unit operations like mixing (Hydration of protein and starch), kneading (homogenization) and shearing (extrusion). Wheat contains important nutritional value such as protein, fiber, lipid, minerals and phytochemicals. Moong beans contain in rich nutrients such as dietary fiber, protein, and oligosaccharide and bioactive phytochemicals. Lipid metabolism of moong beans polyphenols is important. Sprouts are very nutritious as they contain prominent of vitamins A, B, C and E. Quinoa content high protein, balanced amino acid and high content of methionine and lysine and also contain minerals calcium, fiber and iron and rich in antioxidants such as polyphenols.

Key word: Vermicelli, Wheat, Sprouted Moong, Quinoa, Value-added

Introduction

Wheat (genus *Triticum*) is a staple grain globally, with *triticum aestivum* (bread wheat) being the most common species. Its kernel, approximately 1/8–1/4 inch long, is characterized by a brush of stiff hairs and an ovoid shape. Wheat's protein content, influenced by variety, climate, and soil, is rich in glutamine but low in tryptophan (Food science 7th edition B. Shrilakshmi). While the bran and germ offer higher concentrations of essential amino acids compared to the endosperm, wheat itself provides significant nutritional value, including protein, fiber, lipids, minerals, and phytochemicals (Shewry and Hey 2015). It is a versatile ingredient used in numerous products like bread, chapati, pasta, and baked goods (David et al., 2015). Another important grain, quinoa (*chenopodium quinoa*), belonging to the amaranthus family (Bastidas et al., 2016). its small, round, flat seeds that come in various colour rang from black and white to gray also be red and yellow (Nowak et al., 2015). Known as the "mother of grains," quinoa is a nutritional powerhouse, boasting high protein content with a balanced amino acid profile (including lysine and methionine), along with fiber, iron, phosphorus, vitamin B2, and antioxidants (Food science 7th edition B. Shrilakshmi). Similar to wheat in carbohydrate content, quinoa also provides essential minerals and is considered a complete protein. In addition to these grains, and the third nutrient element being used in this investigation is legumes like the *moong* bean (*vigna radiata*), also known as *moong*, are a valuable source of nutrition. These small, round beans are rich in dietary fiber, protein, oligosaccharides, and bioactive phytochemicals (Kalim et al., 2021). Sprouted *moong* beans are particularly nutritious, containing high levels of vitamins A, B, C, and E, although heat processing can diminish their nutritional value. Finally, vermicelli, a traditional indian dish, is a popular extruded food product made from wheat flour. While refining can reduce its nutritional value, value-added vermicelli offers a potential solution to improve nutritional intake and address food supplementation needs. The extrusion process involved in vermicelli production includes mixing, kneading, and shearing, resulting in a convenient and widely consumed food item (Shabbir et al., 2021).

Materials And Methods**Raw materials collections and preparation**

For development and quality assessment of protein rich vermicelli by incorporating with wheat flour, sprouted *moong* flour, quinoa flour. Following material were collected-

Wheat- It is purchased from local market of Bilaspur.

Moong- It is purchased from local market of Bilaspur.

Quinoa- It is purchase from Amazon pantry.

NAAS Rating – 04.17

4.

Oil- It is used for dough do not stick the hand extruder.

5.

Cardboard- It is used for packaging the finished product.

Method

The preparation of value-added vermicelli different compositions of raw materials was used. Proper mixing of wheat flour, sprouted *moong* flour and quinoa flour in different ratio by hand to the formation of dough.

Process**Pre-treatment of wheat**

Sorting- Separating of wheat, there physical properties such as shape, size, density and photometric properties of materials.

Grading- Classification of wheat on the basis of their quality incorporating commercial values and official standards.

Sieve- Separation the wheat from their agricultural waste such as wheat straw, stone etc.

Washing- Washing is done to clean the raw materials.

Drying- After washing, wheat is dried so that the product can be grind properly.

Grinding- After sieving wheat is grind of making of wheat flour.

Pre-treatment of moong

Sorting- Separating of *moong*, there physical properties such as shape, size, density and photometric properties of materials.

Grading- Classification of *moong* on the basis of their quality incorporating commercial values and official standards.

Sieve- Separate the *moong* of their agricultural waste such as *moong* straw, stone etc.

Washing- Washing is done to clean the raw materials.

Germination- *Moong* was soaked overnight then after covered *moong* with wet cloths after 2-3 days *moong* become sprouts.

Peeling- After germination skin off of sprouted *moong*.

Drying- Then after sprouted *moong* are sun dried.

Grinding- After drying *moong* is grind of making of sprouted *moong* flour.

Pre-treatment of quinoa

Sorting- Separating of quinoa, there physical properties such as shape, size, density and photometric properties of materials.

Grading- Classification of quinoa on the basis of their quality incorporating commercial values and official standards.

Sieve- Separate the quinoa of their agricultural waste such as wheat straw, stone etc.

Washing- Washing is done to clean the raw materials.

Drying- After washing, quinoa is dried so that the product can be grind

properly.

Grinding- After drying quinoa is grind of making of quinoa flour.

Process for preparation of vermicelli

Collect all raw dry ingredients (wheat flour, sprouted *moong* flour and quinoa flour) and sieved with sieve to get fine flour and then weight raw dry ingredients.

All the ingredients are mixed together in appropriate ratio and are kneaded to form dough and prepare smooth homogeneous mass.

Dough is allowed and takes some rest, because rest allows the starches and the gluten to expand and fully absorb the water, which makes the dough easier to handle and can shorten the time needed to fully knead the dough.

Roll the dough in clean surface and cut them in small pieces, grease the oil inner surface of the extruder, the reasons of greasing the oil are dough is does not stick to the surface of hand extruder.

Put the dough inside the hand extruder and press the extruder by hand and collect the product.

Take the extruded product and put it on the double boiler for steam cooking of extruded product steam cooks at least 10- 12 min. placed the cooked product on clean tray.

Place the product for drying in sun.

Pack the dry vermicelli in food grade packaging materials and easily store at room temperature.

Results And Discussions

The result of the experiments of value-added vermicelli have been presented and discussed in this chapter. At present time people gives more importance to value added products. For making it more value-able. Added sprouted *moong* flour and quinoa flour to improve the protein percentage of vermicelli. Wheat is containing amount of protein is called gluten it's responsible of unique elasticity and stickiness of dough and wheat also rich source of various antioxidants, vitamins, minerals and fiber. The fiber of wheat bran is arabinoxylan. *Moong* beans sprouts contain prominent of vitamin A, B, C and E. Iron concentration of sprouted *moong* is present in higher amounts and also excellent source of ascorbic acid and riboflavin.

Moong sprouts rich in trypsin inhibitors which can protect the liver, reduced protein breakdown and thereby protect the kidney. *Moong* beans are sure-fire way to support your entire body while itchy skin, rashes and detoxing and strengthen your stomach and liver. Calcium is found higher concentration of dry *moong* and iron concentration is higher in sprouted *moong* sample. Protein and phospholipids can excite nerves and increase appetite, which is necessary to increase the nutrition of many important organs. Quinoa contain high protein, balanced amino acid and high

contains of methionine and lysine and also contains calcium, iron, fiber and rich in antioxidants such as polyphenols. Quinoa is good for beta nine and metabolic syndrome. Quinoa reduced total cholesterol level and LDL (low density lipo-protein) level and increased glutathione quinoa in the diet could decrease oxidative stress, improve serum lipid profile, help to control body weight and serum glucose and decrease cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetic risks.

Four samples prepared are as follows:

1. Wheat flours 50%, Sprouted *moong* flour 40%, Quinoa flour 10%.
2. Wheat flours 50%, Sprouted *moong* flour 30%, Quinoa flour 20%.
3. Wheat flours 50%, Sprouted *moong* flour 20%, Quinoa flour 30%.
4. Wheat flours 50%, Sprouted *moong* flour 10%, Quinoa flour 40%.

Observed that, when the percentage amounts of quinoa are increased it tasted like roughness at the time of eating is also increased and when decreased the percentage amounts of quinoa the tastes like roughness at the time of eating is also decreased. Then out of these four selected sample No. 1 (50% Wheat flour, 40% Sprouted *moong* flour 40%, 10% Quinoa Flour).

Sensory evolution of finished products

Table 1: Sensory evaluation of finished product

Panelist	Appearance	Taste	Texture	Mouthfeel	Flavour	Overall Acceptability
P1	9	8	8	8	8	8
P2	8	7	8	7	7	8
P3	8	8	9	9	9	9
P4	8	8	8	7	8	8
P5	9	9	8	9	8	8
P6	8	9	8	9	9	9
P7	9	8	8	9	9	9

P8	8	8	8	8	8	8
P9	8	8	8	8	8	8
Mean	8.3	8.1	8.1	8.2	8.2	8.3
Variance	0.25	0.36	0.11	0.69	0.44	0.25
Skewness	0.85	0.019	3.0	-0.49	-0.25	0.85
Kurtosis	-1.71	1.126	-1.120	-1.27	-0.04	-1.71
Standard Deviation	0.5	0.60	0.33	0.83	0.66	0.5
Mean Deviation	0.44	0.39	0.19	0.69	0.51	0.44

The sample is prepared by adding

Wheat flour – 50%, Sprouted *moong* flour – 40%, Quinoa flour– 10%.

Nine semi-trained panelists conducted a sensory evaluation. Panelist 1 gave the highest score of 9 for appearance, noting their preference for the vermicelli's color. Panelist 2 gave a maximum score of 8 for both appearance and texture, liking the product's color and thickness. Panelist 3 gave a maximum score of 9 for mouthfeel, texture, and flavor, appreciating the vermicelli's thickness and the taste of sprouted *moong* flour. Panelist 4 gave a minimum score of 7 for mouthfeel, noting a moderate liking due to the quinoa taste. Panelist 5 gave a maximum score of 9 for appearance, taste, and mouthfeel, liking both the vermicelli's color and the taste of quinoa. Panelist 6 gave a minimum score of 8 for

texture and appearance, but a maximum score of 9 for all other parameters. Panelist 7 gave a maximum score of 9 for flavor, appearance, and mouthfeel, appreciating the taste of wheat flour. Panelist 8 gave a maximum score of 8 for all parameters, liking the taste of sprouted *moong*. Panelist 9 gave a maximum score of 8 for all parameters, liking the taste of quinoa and wheat flour. The average scores were: appearance 8.3, taste 8.1, texture 8.1, mouthfeel 8.2, and flavor 8.2. The overall acceptability of the product was 8.3, with the highest score (8.3) in appearance.

Fig. 1: Mean of sensory score

Overall Physico-Chemical Analysis result of final product

S. No.	Parameter	Result (%)
Physico-Chemical Analysis		
1.	Carbohydrates Content	73.06
2.	Protein Content	15.12
3.	pH	6.12
4.	Moisture Content	4.28
5.	Fat Content	3.21
6.	Dietary Fiber	2.58
7.	Ash Content	2.10
8.	Alcoholic Acidity	0.04
9.	Calorific Value	387.31

Table 2: Overall Physico-Chemical Analysis result of final product

Microbial Analysis		
10.	Total Plate Count	169
11.	Salmonella Count	Absent
12.	E. coli Count	Absent

The final product analysis was completed. The vermicelli had a moisture content of 4.28 g/100g, an ash content of 2.10 g/100g, a fat content of 3.21 g/100g, a carbohydrate content of 73.06 g/100g (due to the addition of sprouted *moong* flour and quinoa flour), a protein content of 15.12

g/100g, a dietary fiber content of 2.58 g/100g, and an alcoholic acidity of 0.04 g/100g. The total plate count was 169, while *Salmonella* and *E. coli* were absent.

Fig. 2: Overall Physico-Chemical Analysis result of final product

4.1 Physico-Chemical comparison between value added vermicelli and wheat flour vermicelli

Table 3: Physico-Chemical comparison between value added vermicelli and wheat flour vermicelli

S. No.	PARAMETER	VALUE ADDED VERMICELLI PER (100GM)	WHEAT FLOUR VERMICELLI PER (100 GM)
1.	Carbohydrates	73.06 g	70.39 g
2.	Protein	15.12 g	9.70 g
3.	Moisture	4.28 g	9.59 g
4.	Fat	3.21 g	0.45 g
5.	Ash	2.10 g	0.60 g
6.	Dietary Fiber	2.58 g	9.28 g

Discussion

The prepared sample had a carbohydrate content of 73.06% and a protein content of 15.12%, which is higher than that of commercial wheat flour vermicelli. This increase is due to the addition of sprouted *moong* flour and quinoa flour, which enhanced the protein content. The sample's fat percentage was 3.21%, also higher than that of commercial wheat flour vermicelli, again due to the addition of sprouted *moong* flour and quinoa

flour. The prepared sample's protein content of 15.12% is comparable to the 10.10% protein content reported by Jyotsana et al. (2004) in their study on the effect of additives on the quality and microstructure of vermicelli made from *Triticum aestivum*. This study has the potential to contribute to the future development of value-added vermicelli products with enhanced nutritional profiles, appealing to consumers.

Fig. 3: Physico-Chemical comparison between value added vermicelli and wheat flour vermicelli

4.5 Rehydration of vermicelli

Rehydration of food material is often carried out by soaking the dried material in water (Gracia-Pascual et al., 2005).

Procedure- To check rehydration capacity of vermicelli. Take 5 g of Vermicelli sample was boiled 200 ml of distilled water until optimal cooking time and the water in the surface of boiled vermicelli is removed and find new vermicelli weight (Hastuti et al., 2020).

The rehydration Capacity was calculated by

$$\text{Rehydration capacity (\%)} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100$$

Where

W₂ – Final weight of sample
W₁ – Initial weight of sample
The following sample are-

Sample No. A (WF 50 g, SMF 40 g, QF 10 g)

Initial wt. Of sample – 5.11 g Final wt. Of sample – 18.20 g

Rehydration capacity (%) = $\frac{18.20 - 5.11}{5.11} \times 100$

$15.11 \times 100 = 256.16\%$

1. Sample No. B (WF 50 g, SMF 30 g, QF 20 g)

Initial wt. Of sample – 5.16 g Final wt. Of sample – 18.89 g

Rehydration capacity (%) = $\frac{18.89 - 5.16}{5.16} \times 100$

$5.16 \times 100 = 266.08\%$

Sample No. C (WF 50 g, SMF 20 g, QF 30 g)

Initial wt. Of sample – 5.15 g Final wt. Of sample – 19.20 g

Rehydration capacity (%) = $\frac{19.20 - 5.15}{5.15} \times 100$

$5.15 \times 100 = 272.81\%$

Sample No. D (WF 50 g, SMF 10 g, QF 40 g)

Initial wt. Of sample – 5.12 g Final wt. Of sample – 19.93 g

Rehydration capacity (%) = $\frac{19.93 - 5.12}{5.12} \times 100$

$5.12 \times 100 = 289.25\%$

Discussion-

It was observed that increasing the percentage of quinoa in the vermicelli increased its water absorption properties. Conversely, decreasing the percentage of quinoa decreased water absorption. Therefore, the amount of quinoa is directly proportional to the vermicelli's water absorption capacity.

Summary and Conclusion

Summary

Currently, there is a growing emphasis on value-added food products. To enhance its nutritional value, a value-added vermicelli product was developed using wheat flour, sprouted *moong* flour, and quinoa flour. Vermicelli is a convenient food, requiring only 10-12 minutes to cook. Wheat flour is deficient in lysine, an essential amino acid, and its protein quality is generally poor. The refining process further diminishes its nutritional value. Therefore, value-added vermicelli is important for improving the nutritional profile of this staple food. Value addition also offers a solution to food supplementation and malnutrition. In India, a large portion of the population resides in rural areas with limited access to ready-made and processed foods. Utilizing traditional food processing methods can reduce costs, making processed products more readily available and affordable.

For this value-added product, *moong* beans were soaked overnight, covered with a damp cloth, and allowed to sprout for 2-3 days. The sprouts were then sun-dried for 2-3 days and ground into flour using a mixer grinder, followed by sieving. Sprouted *moong* is rich in protein, fiber, ascorbic acid, and iron, offering various health benefits, including liver protection and reduced protein breakdown, which can benefit kidney health. Quinoa seeds were washed, sun-dried for 1-2 days, and then ground into flour.

The value-added vermicelli was prepared by combining wheat flour, sprouted *moong* flour, and quinoa flour in four different proportions. Sensory evaluation, focusing on taste, appearance, texture, flavor, and mouthfeel, was conducted by nine semi-trained panelists using a 9-point hedonic scale. The mean scores were: appearance 8.3, taste 8.1, texture 8.1, mouthfeel 8.2, and flavor 8.2, with an overall acceptability score of

8.3. The vermicelli was deemed acceptable and exhibited good nutritional value, containing

15.12g of protein, 3.21g of fat, and 2.58g of fiber, thanks to the addition of sprouted *moong* flour and quinoa flour.

Vermicelli is a simple extruded and dried product with a moisture content typically between 4.8 and 7.3g per 100g. This low moisture content contributes to a longer shelf life due to reduced water activity. The low water activity is a primary factor in the extended shelf life, allowing the vermicelli to be stored in simple primary packaging bags for at least 3-6 months at normal room temperature.

Conclusions

It was observed that increasing the percentage of quinoa in the vermicelli increased the sensation of roughness during consumption, while decreasing the quinoa percentage reduced this roughness. Similarly, increasing the percentage of quinoa increased the vermicelli's water absorption properties, and decreasing the quinoa percentage decreased water absorption. Therefore, the amount of quinoa is directly proportional to the vermicelli's water absorption capacity. It was also observed that increasing the percentage of quinoa decreased the extrusion rate of the vermicelli, likely due to the rough texture of quinoa. The final product is rich in nutrients, particularly protein and fiber, compared to other commercially available vermicelli products. The product's quality was deemed good and acceptable, and it can be stored at room temperature for at least one month.

Suggestion For Future Work

Vermicelli is a traditional food in India, also consumed in countries like China, Italy, and the USA. In India, it is prepared and enjoyed in various ways, including sweet dishes like kheer and faluda, as well as savory preparations like upma. Future development of vermicelli could include flavored varieties, such as gulkand vermicelli, or nutritional fortification. Gluten-free vermicelli could also be developed, offering a suitable option for individuals with diabetes or high cholesterol.

References

1. AOAC (1990) official method of food analysis 4th edition vol. 1. Association of analytical chemist. USA.

2. **Arneja, I., Tanwar, B. and Chauhan, A. (2015).** Nutritional composition and health benefits of golden grain of 21st Century, Quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa* Willd.): A review. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 14(12), 1034.
3. **B. Srilakshmi (2018).** Food science 7th edition published by new age international (P) Ltd. Publishers.
4. **Bastidas, E. G., Roura, R., Rizzolo, D. A. D., Massanés, T., and Gomis, R. (2016).** Quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa* Willd.), from nutritional value to potential health benefits: an integrative review. *Journal of Nutrition & Food Sciences*, 2016, vol. 6, num. 3.
5. **Bhathal, S. and Kaur, N. (2015).** Effect of germination on nutrient composition of gluten free Quinoa (*Chenopodium Quinoa*). *Food Science*, 4(10), 423-425.
6. **Chandraprabha, S., Sharon, C. L., Panjikaran, S. T., Aneena, E. R. and Beena, C. (2017).** Development and nutritional qualities of vermicelli prepared from barnyard millet and Ekanayakam root bark. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 6(6), 2359-2362.
7. **David, O., Arthur, E., Kwadwo, S. O., Badu, E., and Sakyi, P. (2015).** Proximate composition and some functional properties of soft wheat flour. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 4(2), 753-758.
8. **Devi, K. P., Prema, R. S., Vaidheswaran, H., Sudha, A. and Sangeetha, V. (2015).** Quality evaluation of non-wheat sweet vermicelli. *International Journal of Engineering and Technoscience*, 1(1), 1-6.
9. **Ezhilarasi, I. C. and Nazni, P. (2018)** Effect of thermal pre-milling treatment on pearl millet and incorporation of psyllium husk in the formulation of vermicelli.
10. **Goel, K., Goomer, S. and Aggarwal, D. (2021).** Formulation and optimization of value-added barnyard millet vermicelli using response surface methodology. *Asian Journal of Dairy and Food Research*, 40(1), 55-61.
11. **Gupta, S. P., Singh, P. K., Vivek, R. K., Chandra, M. S., Verma, S. K., Kumar, A. and Gupta, S. (2022).** Effect of micronutrients application on productivity and profitability of moong bean (*Vigna radiata* L.).
12. **Hastuti, R. P., Sasongko, S. B. and Djaeni, M. (2021).** Rehydration capacity of vermicelli prepared by combining arenga starch, rice flour and sorghum. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* (Vol. 1053, No. 1, p. 012115). IOP Publishing.
13. **Hernández-Ledesma, B. (2019).** Quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa* Willd.) as source of bioactive compounds: A review. *Bioactive Compounds in Health and Disease*, 2(3), 27-47.
14. **Jacobsen, S. E., Mujica, A. and Jensen, C. R. (2003).** The resistance of quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa* Willd.) to adverse abiotic factors. *Food reviews international*, 19(1-2), 99-109.
15. **Jancurová, M., Minarovičová, L., & Dandar, A. (2009).** Quinoa—a review. *Czech Journal of Food Sciences*, 27(2), 71-79.
16. **Jyoti, S., Krishna, K., Abigail, Y., Sourav, S., Sawinder, K., Yogesh, G. and Prasad, R. (2018).** Optimisation of a process for cocoa-based vermicelli. *Foods and Raw materials*, 6(2), 291-295.
17. **Jyotsna, R., Prabhasankar, P., Indrani, D. and Rao, G. V. (2004).** Effect of additives on the quality and microstructure of vermicelli made from *Triticum aestivum*. *European Food Research and Technology*, 218(6), 557-562.
18. **Kalim, A., Zaheer, M., Siddiqui, M. U. A., Ahmed, S. and Hassan, M. M. (2021).** Nutritional value, Ethnomedicine, Phytochemistry and pharmacology of *Vigna radiata* (L.) R. Wilczek. *J. pharmacogn. phytochem*, 10(2), 54-58.
19. **Mehta, N., Rao, P. and Saini, R. (2021).** A review on metabolites and pharmaceutical potential of food legume crop mung bean (*Vigna radiata* L.). *Bio Technologia. Journal of Biotechnology Computational Biology and Bionanotechnology*, 102(4).
20. **Mogra, R. and Midha, S. (2013).** Value addition of traditional wheat flour vermicelli. *Journal of food science and technology*, 50(4), 815-820.
21. **Narwal, N. and Nutan Narwal, C. (2017).** Development and nutritional evaluation of value-added extruded products from maize-oat-tulsi flour blend. *International Journal of Home Science*, 3, 427-429.
22. **Nowak, V., Du, J. and Charrondière, U. R. (2016).** Assessment of the nutritional composition of quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa* Willd.). *Food chemistry*, 193, 47-54.
23. **Pahwa, A., Khamrui, K. and Prasad, W. (2020).** Influence of oat flour on pasting properties of flour blends, cooking quality and sensory attributes of vermicelli. *The Annals of the University Dunarea de Jos of Galati. Fascicle VI-Food Technology*, 44(2), 70-84.
24. **Pahwa, A., Khamrui, K. and Prasad, W. (2020).** Influence of oat flour on pasting properties of flour blends, cooking quality and sensory attributes of vermicelli. *The Annals of the University Dunarea de Jos of Galati. Fascicle VI-Food Technology*, 44(2), 70-84.
25. **Pandey, P., Malagi, U., Yenagi, N. and Fatima, A. (2017).** Optimization of Value-Added Vermicelli Based on Foxtail Millet (*Setaria italica*). *Int. J. Pure App. Biosci*, 5(2), 871-879.
26. **Prabhasankar, P., Rajiv, J., Indrani, D. and Rao, G. V. (2007).** Influence of whey protein concentrate, additives, their combinations on the quality and microstructure of vermicelli made from Indian T. Durum wheat variety. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 80(4), 1239-1245.
27. **Rajiv, J., Inamdar, A. A., Sakhare, S. and Venkateswara Rao, G. (2015).** Roller milled black gram (*Phaseolus mungo*) semolina and its influence on the quality characteristics of high protein pasta. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 52(4), 2464-2468.
28. **Ramos Martín, C., Royo Gracia, P., Lanfranchi, M., Pellinghelli, M. A. and Tiripicchio, A. (2005).** Zirconium and hafnium complexes with (allylsilyl) (η -amidosilyl)- η -5-cyclopentadienyl ligands: synthesis, structure and reactivity.
29. **Repo-Carrasco, R., Espinoza, C. and Jacobsen, S. E. (2003).** Nutritional value and use of the Andean crops quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa*) and kañiwa (*Chenopodium pallidicaule*). *Food reviews international*, 19(1-2), 179-189.
30. **Reynolds, M., Foulkes, J., Furbank, R., Griffiths, S., King, J., Murchie, E. and Slafer, G. (2012).** Achieving yield gains in wheat. *Plant, cell & environment*, 35(10), 1799-1823.
31. **Ronge, B. V., Padghan, P. V., Jayabhaye, R. V. and Patil, R. A. (2017).** Effect of Skim Milk Powder on Sensory Parameters of Vermicelli. *Journal of Ready to Eat Food* | January-March, 4(01), 01-05.
32. **Savage, G. P. (1990).** Nutritional value of sprouted mung beans. *Nutrition Today*, 25(3), 21-24.
33. **Shabbir, S. T., Trisa, P. and Bhagat Sachin, S. (2021)** Effect of various environmental conditions on the nutraceutical value of some common edible sprouts.
34. **Shahrajabian, M. H., Sun, W. and Cheng, Q. (2019).** A short review of health benefits and nutritional values of mung bean in

- sustainable agriculture. Polish Journal of Agronomy, 37, 31-36.
35. Shewry, P. R. (2009). Wheat. Journal of experimental botany, 60(6), 1537- 1553.
36. **Shewry, P. R. and Hey, S. J. (2015).** The contribution of wheat to human diet and health. Food and energy security, 4(3), 178-202.
37. **Shewry, P. R. and Hey, S. J. (2015).** The contribution of wheat to human diet and health. Food and energy security, 4(3), 178-202.
38. **Singh, A., Jaiswal, M., Agrahari, K. and Singh, A. (2017).** Standardization and development of moong dal-based products. International Journal of Home Science, 3(1), 358-362.
39. **Sirirat, S., Charutigon, C. and Rungsardthong, V. (2005).** Preparation of rice vermicelli by direct extrusion. The Journal of KMITNB, 15(1), 39-45.
40. **Tiwari, U., Servan, A. and Nigam, D. (2017).** Comparative study on antioxidant activity, phytochemical analysis and mineral composition of the Mung Bean (*Vigna Radiata*) and its sprouts. J Pharmacog Phytochem, 6(1), 336.
41. **Vetrimani, R., Sudha, M. L. and Rao, P. H. (2005).** Effect of extraction rate of wheat flour on the quality of vermicelli. Food Research International, 38(4), 411-416